

Oxidation of Secondary Alcohols by Pyridinium Fluorochromate in Aqueous Acetic Acid Medium : A Kinetic and Mechanistic Study

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A new oxidising reagent, viz. pyridinium fluorochromate¹ (PFC) has been developed recently and found to have several advantages over similar oxidising agents. The present paper describes the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of propan-2-ol, butan-2-ol and pentan-2-ol.

Results and Discussion

The plot of log absorbance vs time is linear indicating that the order with respect to PFC is unity. The near constancy in the values of k_{obs} irrespective of concentration of PFC confirms the first order dependence on PFC. The rate of oxidation is increased progressively on increasing the concentration of alcohol (Table 1). Moreover, the plot of log k_{obs} vs log [alcohol] is also linear with a unit slope. It indicates that the order with respect

to alcohol is unity. Plot of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[alcohol]$ is linear and does not make a positive intercept on reaction ordinate. This indicates that no kinetically detectable complex is formed during oxidation.

The rate of oxidation of alcohol is affected considerably by changing the solvent polarity of acetic acid-water mixture. The plot of log k_{obs} vs inverse of dielectric constant is linear with a positive slope indicating interaction between ion and a dipole².

The rate of oxidation is increased by the addition of paratoluene sulphonic acid (PTSA) (Table 2) when volume percentage of acetic acid is kept constant. In presence of acid, PFC may be protonated. The protonated PFC may function as the effective oxidant species similar to the chromium trioxide oxidation,

TABLE 1—RATE DATA FOR THE OXIDATION OF PROPAN-2-OL, BUTAN-2-OL AND PENTAN-2-OL

Solvent	HOAC	H ₂ O = 4	1 (v/v)	Temp	$\times 10^4 k_{obs} (s^{-1})$		
					Propan-2-ol	Butan-2-ol	Pentan-2-ol
$\times 10^2$ [Substrate]	$\times 10^3$ [PFC]	$\times 10^3$ [NaNO ₃]	K				
mol dm ⁻³	mol dm ⁻³	mol dm ⁻³					
10	10	100	313	2.4	3.3	3.9	
20	10	100	313	4.9	6.4	7.6	
30	10	100	313	7.6	10.6	11.7	
40	10	100	313	10.3	14.5	15.4	
10	10	100	308	1.9	2.5	3.2	
10	10	100	318	3.3	4.3	4.7	
10	10	100	323	4.4	5.3	6.0	
10	10	100	328	5.3	6.9	7.4	
10	10	100	333	6.9	7.2	9.0	
10	10	10	313	2.5	3.4	3.8	
10	10	50	313	2.6	3.5	3.9	

Mechanism : The rate of oxidation depends not only on the concentration of alcohol and PFC but also on hydrogen ion concentration. On this basis the following rate law may be proposed for the oxidation reaction,

$$\frac{-d[\text{PFC}]}{dt} = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{PFC}] [\text{Alcohol}] [\text{H}^+]^x \quad (3)$$

With the available data the dependence on hydrogen ion concentration may not be predicted exactly. At constant $[\text{H}^+]$ the rate law (3) reduces to (4),

$$\frac{-d[\text{PFC}]}{dt} = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{PFC}] [\text{Alcohol}] \quad (4)$$

Based on the kinetic data, the proposed mechanism is shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of reagent grade. The alcohols were dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and then fractionally distilled. Propan-2-

ol- α -D was prepared⁶ by the reaction of acetone with sodium and D_2O . Acetic acid was purified by standard methods. PFC was synthesised by the literature method¹. Conductivity water was used to prepare aqueous solutions. All the reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order condition keeping an excess of [alcohol] over [PFC]. The reaction was followed colorimetrically by observing the absorbance at 420 nm (Erma AE11S) at different time intervals. As in the case of titrimetric method a separate thermostat was used. The rate constants were reproducible within $\pm 4\%$.

Product analysis and stoichiometry : The product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions, i.e. with an excess of substrate over the oxidant. The products of oxidation were the corresponding ketones and were identified by their DNP derivatives. Hence the oxidation can be represented by equation (5),

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